

The Infrastructural Power of Time: Policymaking in Lebanon

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How do political systems use time as a governance tool and how does this usurp people's time in the process? The relationship between time and politics, referred to as chronopolitics, has been the focus of significant scholarly work (Esposito and Becker, 2023). However, this concept has yet to gain substantial recognition within the field of Middle East political studies. In this paper, I explore how policymaking in Lebanon relies on varying governance tempos and, in so doing, functions as a form of infrastructural power.¹ This includes alternating between protracted inaction and fast-paced action across various policy sectors, as well as enacting both action and inaction *within* the same policy realm.

Post-Civil War Lebanon is often depicted as a weak state with limited capacity to control its borders and respond to overlapping crises from the management of waste to multiple geopolitical insecurities (Hale 2024).² However, this apparent weakness hides a latent dimension of power: How the state draws on time to manage crises and regulate rights and service provision. Analyzing the politics of time and its infrastructural power, and how this power 'sits' within Lebanon's political system, unlocks new perspectives on the

Lebanese state.

An Assemblage of Temporalities

Lebanon's political system operates on a complex sectarian model of power-sharing, where recurrent deadlocks and veto-playing frequently hinder policymaking (Doyle 2021). It is often reported that deadlocks arise from the architecture of the power-sharing system, in which sectarian factions, driven by their competing interests, derail the consensus required to address controversies. Sectarian factions have often held veto power in the cabinet which has occasionally resulted in the cabinet's collapse. A notable example is the 2011 collapse of the Saad Hariri government following a walkout by ministers affiliated with the Shia-based Hezbollah party and their allies (Fakhoury 2019, 12).

Notwithstanding this, the politics of gridlock requires a more nuanced perspective. Sectarian power-sharing draws on clock time in various ways to sustain its longevity while creating an atmosphere of confusion. Inaction that appears to be a stubborn and inevitable result of the system's architecture actually conceals a sophisticated infrastructure of

1 This paper is inspired by my book project, *Political Systems and Time: Timekeeping in Post-War Lebanon*.

2 The author's interviews and conversations with international officials and experts reinforce this perception.

time management.

In my ongoing book project (Fakhoury 2023), I delve into what I call a ‘political ethnography of time,’ distinguishing between the technology of governance in slow times and frantic times. The post-war sectarian order governs people’s time through a rhythm that alternates between slow-burning and fast-burning crises (On this concept see Seabrooke and Tsingou 2019). Against this backdrop, it is important to examine how the government may alternate governance tempos between different policy sectors and use both slow and fast governance within the same sector.

Alternating Slow and Fast Policy Time

In the post-war period, the process of policymaking—from suggesting, discussing to implementing policy proposals—has consisted of erratic tempos that have alternated between inaction and bursts of frenetic action. Governments have rarely issued budgets or solutions to recent financial crises. This is indicative of ‘slow times’ politics. Amidst the 2019 financial meltdown, caused by political and business elites entangled in a Ponzi scheme that depleted the state’s treasury (Sawaya et al. 2023), little has been done to help people recover their savings. Yet, to divert focus from the state’s policy vacuum and promote their role as moral and security guardians of their communities, the governing elite have quickly organized crackdowns against LGBTQ individuals and refugees (Fakhoury 2024). Given that some ministers have reaped significant political and economic benefits from policy paralysis in the power sector, almost no actions have been taken to fix Lebanon’s crumbling electricity infrastructure (Verdeil 2018). Yet, in 2023, the

government engaged in aggressive advocacy against the United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees (UNRWA) and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), asking them to settle electricity fees for refugees in camps (Mohnblatt 2023). Traffic management and highway maintenance have been at the bottom of the policy-making ladder. Yet, through the Twitter account of the city’s Traffic Management Center, the Ministry of Interior regularly sends messages to organize citizens’ mobility (Monroe 2017). In doing so, bureaucracies project authority and perform urgency while avoiding the urgent issue of maintaining and upgrading roads. Analyzing policy action versus inaction over time and across various policy sectors reveals how a political system can normalize crisis as a mechanism for governing people’s access to resources.

Slowing down time through various tactics, such as delaying the integration of policy items into the policymaking agenda, refusing to advance bills into law, or declining to repeal contested laws, is a significant indicator of how the Lebanese state controls people’s access to rights. Groups such as women, LGBTIQ+ communities and refugees have been stuck within the cracks of time. Consider the stunted development of the citizenship bill that would allow women to pass their nationality on to their children despite ongoing debates on reforming the law (Pollard 2016). Take the 534 Law that criminalizes homosexuality and that, despite contention from below, has stood the test of time (Nagle and Fakhoury 2021). Still, it is not only about ‘*doing nothing*’ through strategic inaction, stalling, or procrastination. Within the same policy sector, as the below example reveals, the Lebanese state may concurrently use different governance tempos to regulate an issue.

Simultaneous Temporalities: Doing Nothing and Doing Something at the Same Time

The contrasting tempos of slow and fast governance manifest in various ways. Refugee governance is a core policy sector where contradictory temporalities play out. Consider the case of the Palestinian refugee camps that remain ‘frozen in time’ with hardly any rights granted to them even though they have been refugees for decades. In this case, the state maximizes slow *clock time*. Drawing on the myth that Palestinians’ access to resources and jobs would tip the sectarian balance of power, the Lebanese parliament has resisted addressing a bill that would improve their access to the labor market. Finally, in 2010, the parliament adopted a bill approving that Palestinians acquire some rights to work as foreigners, but they would be barred from working in about 39 syndicated professions (Bakri 2010). Alternating between doing nothing over long periods of time, such as refraining from legislating, and intermittent policy activity, only to relapse into stagnation, has been a purposeful tactic to keep Palestinian refugees socially excluded and spatially segregated.

In yet another perspective, consider the frantic temporalities of regulating displacement from Syria where the state has abruptly gone from a policy of open borders to one of acute securitization to govern Syrian refugees’ lives and legal residencies. From 2011 until 2014, the Government of Lebanon (GoL) has shifted from welcoming borders to stringent security measures. In 2015, it adopted procedures categorizing Syrians’ stay into more than seven visas and instructed the UNHCR to stop registering Syrian refugees. By issuing onerous residencies for Syrians that expire in a short-term span, the government used

short-time horizons to create persistent precarity. In 2023, the government announced plans to repatriate 15,000 Syrians monthly (UNU-CPR 2023), setting timelines widely viewed as unrealistic.

What drives the state’s logic of ‘slow time’ versus ‘frantic time’ governance within the same policy sector? Why does the state rush to regulate an issue through frantic policy tempos as the Syrian refugee issue reveals while it hardly enacts new laws or policies in other cases, for example the case of Palestinian refugees? A temporal lens enables us to track patterns and types of policy action and inaction across different policy sectors and within the same sector. Contrary to the assumption that the Lebanese state is inefficient, it generates various temporalities of governance, ranging from ‘calculated inaction’ (McConnell and ‘t Hart 2019) to hesitant action to frantic action. Understanding the drivers behind these temporalities requires a contextualized understanding. Motives range from shifting responsibility, distracting the public sphere to sustaining the political economy of sectarianism (Baumann 2024; Fakhoury 2024; 2023). A typology of the state’s patchwork of governance tempos, their drivers, and their motives is what I explore in my current work. ♦

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